

obtained at $\bar{n}_A=1.5$. These values were further corroborated from the plots of

$$\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A} \right] \text{ vs } B \text{ and } \log \left[\frac{2-\bar{n}_A}{\bar{n}_A-1} \right] \text{ vs } B \text{ respectively.}$$

\bar{n} and pL values were calculated and \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complex-ion equilibria. From the formation curves, the values of stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were evaluated which correspond to 1:1 complex at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1:2 complex at $\bar{n}=1.5$ respectively. These were further corroborated by plotting $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}} \right]$ vs pL and $\log \left[\frac{2-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}-1} \right]$ vs pL graphs, respectively.

The formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complex is represented below:

In all the cases, stabilities of 1:1 complexes were evaluated, while in the cases of Y^{3+} , Nd^{3+} and Gd^{3+} stabilities of 1:2 complexes were also evaluated. The $\log K_2$ for others could not be evaluated due to precipitation probably due to metal ion hydrolysis. The order of stability of trivalent metal-chelates was found to be

TABLE I—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

Cations	t = 25°C					
	H ⁺	Y ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺
Log K ₁	11.38	7.82	7.73	6.88	7.66	7.45
Log K ₂	3.80	7.02	—	6.18	6.83	—

* For proton association (H⁺), K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species LH and LH₂⁺ respectively, while for metal ions K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species ML₁ and ML₂ respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to record their sincere thanks to Dr. D. G. Vartak, B.A.R.C., Bombay for the valuable suggestions and to Prof. A. P. Rao, Vice-Principal, Ramnarain Ruia College, Bombay, for

his kind and continuous encouragement in accomplishing this work.

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Quinoxaline Complexes with Some Mercury(II) Salts

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Manuscript received 25 June 1979, revised 5 May 1980, accepted 21 May 1980

THE complexes of quinoxaline (Q) with several transition metal salts have been studied by various workers¹⁻⁵ and here are described those formed by interaction with Hg(II) chloride, bromide, cyanide and thiocyanate. These complexes have been characterized by molar conductance, molecular weight, IR and far-IR spectral measurements down to 200 cm⁻¹.

The chloro-, bromo- and cyano-complexes were prepared by adding an excess of the ligand solution in ethanol to a hot solution of the metal salt in the same solvent. The thiocyanato complex was prepared by boiling a suspension of the metal thiocyanate with an excess of the ligand in ethanol and filtering the solution hot. The complexes which precipitated or crystallized out were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuo. Hg(Q)Cl₂: m.p. 256 [Found: Hg, 50.40; Cl, 17.29, Calc.: Hg, 49.87; Cl, 17.70%]; Hg₂(Q)Br₄: m.p. 243 [Found: Hg, 46.88; Br, 36.67, Calc.: Hg, 47.07; Br, 37.64%]; Hg(Q)(CN)₂: m.p. >290 [Found: Hg, 52.50; Calc.: Hg, 52.35%]; Hg(Q)(SCN)₂: m.p. 176 d. [Found: Hg, 44.12; SCN, 26.32, Calc.: Hg, 44.84; SCN, 26.00%].

Molar conductance of 10⁻³M solutions in DMF (Philips Conductivity Bridge) indicate them to be non-electrolytes, except the thiocyanato-complex which acts as a weak electrolyte. The IR spectra of

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the complexes recorded in Nujol mulls with a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer are similar to those of quinoxaline complexes with other metal salts¹⁻⁵, conforming coordination of the two ligand-N atoms to different metal ions, the ligand thus acting as a bidentate bridge (steric positions of nitrogen atoms in quinoxaline precludes chelation). In addition to the absorption bands due to coordinated quinoxaline, the far-IR spectra of the chloro- and bromo-complexes show the halogen dependent terminal^{6,7} Hg-X stretching modes at 320 and 225 cm⁻¹, respectively. The bridging Hg-Br stretching mode in bromo-complex expected at ~150 cm⁻¹ could not be recorded with the present range of the spectrophotometer. However, the molecular weight of the bromo-complex determined by Rast's method (obs. 810, calc. 850) is consistent with the dimeric structure. The molecular weights of the other complexes could not be determined by this method as they were insoluble in camphor.

The IR spectrum of the cyano-complex shows additional absorption bands at 2183, 421 and 325 cm⁻¹ which are identified as $\nu(\text{CN})$, $\nu(\text{HgC})$ and $\delta(\text{HgCN})$ modes respectively, due to coordinated terminal cyano groups⁸. The frequency of $\nu(\text{CN})$ suffers a significant negative shift when the cyano bridges break down and mercury(II) cyanide complexes with terminal cyano groups absorb at lower frequencies than pure mercury(II) cyanide containing bridging cyano groups⁸. Furthermore, $\nu(\text{HgC})$ shift to higher frequencies in complexes containing bridging cyano groups and this positive shift may be attributed to coupling of $\nu(\text{HgC})$ with $\nu(\text{CN})$ in the HgCN part of the molecule. Since terminal cyano groups absorb at lower frequencies than pure $\text{Hg}(\text{CN})_2$, the terminal $\nu(\text{HgC})$ and $\delta(\text{HgCN})$ modes would also be expected to absorb at lower energies as are observed here for terminally bonded cyano groups⁸. The thiocyanato-complex shows absorption bands at 2117, 717 and 439 cm⁻¹ which are assigned as $\nu(\text{CN})$, $\nu(\text{CS})$ and $\delta(\text{SCN})$, respectively, of the coordinated thiocyanato groups. The frequencies of these modes are consistent with those normally associated with terminal S-bonded thiocyanato groups^{9,10}.

From spectral results it is suggested that chloro-, cyano- and thiocyanato-complexes have polymeric four-coordinated tetrahedral geometry around the metal atoms with two terminally bonded anionic groups and the two nitrogens of the bidentate bridging quinoxaline molecules. The bromo-complex has been assigned a dimeric four-coordinated structure involving both bridging as well as terminal bromide ions.

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Optimal Temperature (T_{opt}) for Maximal Thermal Conductivity (K_{max}) of Solids at Low Temperatures**

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Manuscript received 28 April 1980, accepted 12 June 1980

IN continuation of our earlier communication¹, we now discuss the success of the said equation by calculating the T_{opt} value for many solids to the second order of approximation (S.O.A.) and examine the improvement achieved thereby over the value obtained for the same to the first order of approximation (F.O.A.) in respect of the latest reported^{2,3,4} observed values.

The three-term-thermal conductivity equation, which has been successfully utilized for obtaining a meaningful and informative reduced low-temperature thermal conductivity expression⁵ for solids of widely varying nature, embracing metals, semi-conductors, insulators including molecular crystals and chemical compounds, has been expressed¹ as

$$K = \frac{T}{\alpha + \delta T^2 + \gamma T^3} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{1}{K} = \frac{\alpha}{T} + \delta T + \gamma T^2 \quad \dots (1)$$

from which the expression for T_{opt} is obtained¹ as

$$T_{\text{opt}} = (\alpha/4\gamma)^{1/3} \left\{ \left[1 + \sqrt{1 - \delta^3/27\alpha\gamma^2} - \delta^3/54\alpha\gamma^2 \right]^{1/3} + \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \delta^3/27\alpha\gamma^2} - \delta^3/54\alpha\gamma^2 \right]^{1/3} \right\} - \delta/6\gamma \quad \dots (2)$$

where, according to the most recent views⁶, α , δ and γ are constants being respectively related to the scattering of phonons by geometrical factors including impurities, the effect of anharmonic coupling

** The paper has been submitted for Oral presentation at the Convention of Chemists to be held at I.I.T., Bombay (Powai) in December, 1980.